

FHIR Lens: A Graph-Based Approach to Semantic EHR Exploration

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Abstract—Interoperability in healthcare data remains challenging, especially when exploring complex relationships within data modeled as Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR). While FHIR standardizes data exchange, traditional visualization methods often fail to capture its semantic richness. This paper introduces *FHIR Lens*, an interactive graph-based platform that enhances FHIR exploration through RDF. It leverages SPARQL for dynamic query execution and employs recursive graph expansion to traverse structured healthcare data, addressing challenges like blank nodes and inconsistent references. By visualizing FHIR resources as interconnected nodes and edges, FHIR Lens supports advanced data analysis, relationship discovery, and decision support, contributing to semantic interoperability in healthcare by bridging data standards with graph-based modeling. We describe the platform’s functionality and underlying algorithms and evaluate its performance on increasingly large FHIR datasets. Results indicate that the tool can easily handle exploration and summarization of large FHIR patient graphs, facilitating an intuitive understanding of complex clinical relationships.

Index Terms—RDF, Graph Exploration, Interactive Visualization, FHIR, SPARQL, Healthcare Data

I. INTRODUCTION

Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR)¹ is a standardized framework developed by Health Level Seven International (HL7)², a not-for-profit standards development organization focused on exchanging, integrating, sharing, and retrieving electronic health information. FHIR enables interoperability between disparate health information systems through a set of modular components known as *resources*. However, while FHIR is excellent for interoperability and data exchange, it does not lend itself to exploration and analysis. Consider a researcher reviewing a patient’s longitudinal record involving multiple encounters, lab results, and medications. Navigating these relationships in tabular JSON or XML form is cumbersome and cognitively demanding.

The Resource Description Framework (RDF) [1] is a standard data interchange model developed by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C). It represents information using

triples, each consisting of a subject, predicate, and object, forming a directed, labeled graph structure. RDF facilitates data integration and semantic interoperability by enabling machines to understand relationships between data entities across diverse sources.

Leveraging RDF with FHIR offers a powerful solution to enable interoperability of healthcare data, which becomes even more essential as healthcare technology advances. RDF enables intuitive and structured data navigation, unlike traditional FHIR data formats, such as JSON [2] and XML [3], which lack semantic enrichment. Thus, going back to our example, a graph-based view allows our researcher to follow connections naturally, linking, for instance, a high blood pressure observation directly to a corresponding medication request and its prescribing physician.

Despite RDFs and FHIR’s potential to enhance healthcare data interoperability, visualization, and implementation, challenges persist [4], [5]. Current FHIR visualization tools rely on JSON or XML, failing to represent complex medical relationships as interconnected nodes [6], [7]. RDF visualization tools, on the other hand, struggle with illustrating specific concepts, such as blank nodes, thereby limiting usability and scalability. Blank nodes in RDF are nodes without explicit identifiers, often used to represent anonymous or unspecified resources. Consider for example, in RDF notation, the triple $\{ _ : b0 ; fhir:Patient.name ; "John Doe" \}$. Here, $_ : b0$ is a blank node representing an anonymous patient. Visualization tools typically face difficulties in clearly representing and distinguishing these anonymous nodes, leading to ambiguity in graphical representations. The lack of specialized RDF tools tailored for FHIR further hampers adoption, restricting intelligent healthcare data management and cross-domain integration.

This paper introduces *FHIR Lens*, an interactive platform leveraging Semantic Web technologies [8], such as RDF and SPARQL, to enhance FHIR data visualization and interaction. FHIR Lens bridges traditional healthcare data formats with graph-based models, providing interactive visualizations, SPARQL-powered queries, and recursive exploration algo-

¹<https://hl7.org/fhir/>

²<https://www.hl7.org/>

gorithms. Representing FHIR resources as graphs ensures that the data is (FAIR): findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. The platform enhances semantic interoperability in biomedical research, demonstrating the potential of RDF for FHIR in modern healthcare informatics. In particular, it addresses technical challenges, such as blank node traversal and inconsistent references, while enabling intuitive querying and navigation.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. The formal background is presented in Section II, covering fundamental concepts related to RDF, SPARQL, and FHIR. Related work is discussed in Section III, providing an overview of existing RDF visualization tools and graph exploration techniques. The design and implementation of FHIR Lens is presented in Section IV. Section V demonstrates a practical use case of the system. In Section VI, we evaluate the system’s performance. Finally, Section VII concludes the paper with a summary and an outlook to future work.

II. PRELIMINARIES

RDF represents data as triples in the form of subject–predicate–object, which mirrors the basic Subject–Verb–Object (SVO) structure of English sentences. These triples form the basis of a graph-based data model, where each triple is visualized as a directed edge from the subject node to the object node, with the predicate describing the relationship between them $\text{subject} \xrightarrow{\text{predicate}} \text{object}$. RDF terms consist of Internationalized Resource Identifiers (IRIs) [9], literals, and blank nodes [10]. IRIs serve as globally unique identifiers; literals represent values with explicit data types, and blank nodes allow the representation of complex structures without assigning a global identifier.

Ontologies provide formal, structured representations of knowledge domains by defining classes, properties, and the relationships between them [11]. They enable semantic interoperability by offering shared vocabularies and logical constraints over RDF data. The Web Ontology Language (OWL) [12] builds on RDF to support rich ontology modeling, including class hierarchies, property characteristics (e.g., transitivity, symmetry), and logical axioms for reasoning. OWL ontologies are encoded in RDF, making them compatible with RDF tools and infrastructure, while enabling more expressive semantics for applications that require formal logic and inference.

FHIR¹, developed by HL7², is a healthcare interoperability standard using modular resources such as `Patient` and `Observation`. These resources are represented as nodes in the graph, with `Patient.Identifier` and `Observation.subject.reference` serving as relationships that establish connections between entities. FHIR supports extensibility, integrates with web technologies, and includes security features compliant with GDPR³. Its structured approach ensures adaptability across healthcare systems while maintaining interoperability. Originally represented in

hierarchical forms such as JSON and XML, a canonical RDF representation for FHIR (hereafter FHIR RDF) was defined in the FHIR Standard for Trial Use 3 (STU3) release [13].

SPARQL [14], the standard query language for RDF, enables graph-based querying through pattern matching, solution modifiers, and multiple query result types. It supports advanced features, such as optional patterns, aggregation, sub-queries, and negation, allowing efficient querying across heterogeneous RDF datasets. By providing structured data retrieval and integration capabilities, SPARQL enhances the usability of RDF in diverse applications.

III. RELATED WORK

This section reviews general graph layout strategies and other RDF visualization tools, positioning FHIR Lens with respect to the state-of-the-art.

A. Graph Layout Strategies

Graph layout strategies are essential in graph drawing, network visualization, data representation, and optimizing layouts to reduce edge crossings and improve interpretability.

Force-directed layouts [15], [16] uses attractive and repulsive forces to achieve balanced graph structures. Gansner et al. [17] later improved the computational efficiency of force-directed graphs while maintaining quality. However, these methods struggle with large graphs, requiring adaptations like multi-level layouts and GPU acceleration.

Hierarchical layouts, based on Sugiyama’s framework [18], structure directed graphs through layering, sequencing, and coordinate assignment. The YWorks hierarchical layout [19] effectively minimizes edge crossings with software engineering and biological network applications.

Graph clustering organizes large networks into meaningful subgroups. Spectral clustering [20] and bioconnected components clustering [21] detect robustly connected subgraphs. Girvan and Newman’s edge betweenness clustering [22] reveals community structures by iteratively removing high-betweenness edges. Scalable clustering methods now integrate parallel processing and deep learning to enhance performance in massive datasets [23].

The proposed tool, FHIR Lens, employs a force-directed layout to provide an intuitive visualization of FHIR resources and their relationships. This approach allows users to dynamically explore complex healthcare data structures, ensuring that relationships between entities remain clear and interpretable. The sensitivity of force-directed layouts to large graphs is mitigated by the fact that the exploration tool would typically be used to examine a single patient or observation, while other tools in FHIR Lens provide more aggregate views for multi-patient or sub-graph analytics.

B. RDF Visualization Tools

RDF visualizers are essential for exploring and interacting with RDF data through intuitive graphical representations. Various tools offer distinct features for RDF and ontology visualization.

³<https://gdpr-info.eu/>

RDF Grapher [24] provides static RDF graph representations but lacks interactivity and advanced filtering. WebVOWL [25] focuses on OWL ontologies, offering an intuitive interface for class hierarchies and relationships, but is unable to handle instance-level data in RDF representation as required by FHIR RDF.

YASGUI [26] enhances RDF interaction with SPARQL query execution, result visualization, and syntax validation, supporting tabular views, charts, and geospatial mapping. Wikidata Query Service [27] integrates RDF visualization with the Wikidata knowledge graph, enabling graph-based representations, timelines, and geographical mapping, showcasing linked data visualization for large-scale knowledge graphs.

In contrast to these tools, FHIR Lens improves upon them by integrating their best features into a single platform and offering more. It supports RDF triples and ontologies, provides a rich set of visualization options, including graph-based, and offers full SPARQL query support. Moreover, its user-friendly interface and comprehensive approach make it the most complete tool for visualizing and interacting with RDF and ontology-based datasets. Table I presents a detailed comparison of these tools.

IV. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

FHIR Lens aims to provide a visually intuitive and interactive representation of FHIR resources. It allows users to explore and analyze the data provided in RDF, potentially using blank nodes. FHIR Lens supports access restriction to registered users only. Its graphical interface enables users to explore relationships between nodes and edges visually, supporting interactions such as zooming, panning, dragging, and repositioning nodes. Users can also search for resources by IRI and examine their structure. Additionally, FHIR Lens allows users to explore a resource by double-clicking on the corresponding node, revealing its connections to related elements.

Architecturally, FHIR Lens consists of three core components: frontend, backend, and a triplestore (Figure 1). All components are containerized in Docker, and a Docker Compose orchestration file allows them to be easily deployed as one system. We provide the codebase publicly⁴.

- The frontend serves as the primary user interface, handling data retrieval and interaction on the client side. Development was done using Angular⁵ version 17.3, with Vis.js used for graph drawing. The graph layout used for visualization is force-directed.
- The backend functions as the API, responsible for retrieving FHIR data and managing additional elements such as users and queries. Java Spring Boot⁶ was employed for the backend.
- A triplestore manages RDF resources and provides a SPARQL endpoint for executing queries. During devel-

opment, GraphDB version 10.6.4⁷ was used as the triplestore, as it provides the SPARQL endpoint accessible with `org.eclipse.rdf4j`⁸.

A. Retrieving SPARQL Query Results

FHIR Lens also includes a query interface, enabling users to write and execute structured queries using SPARQL and reviewing the results stored in the database. Furthermore, the application provides functionalities for generating graph statistics, offering insights into the structure and complexity of the data. In our implementation, we use SPARQL 1.1 in combination with GraphDB as a triplestore. The data between the triplestore and backend is exchanged in JSON format.

B. Expansion Algorithm

Complex RDF structures with blank nodes require specialized handling to maintain data consistency. Algorithm 1 recursively expands downstream connections from a source node IRI, taking a resource IRI and a depth parameter as input. A depth of zero initiates expansion from the source node.

If a neighboring node is a blank node, the method recursively calls itself with `depth+1`, ensuring proper linking. Upstream expansion retrieves incoming edges, while downstream expansion identifies outgoing edges.

The output is a list of triples – source node, edge label, and target node – forming an interconnected graph. Since the algorithm does not handle redundancy, a Boolean flag can track recursion levels. Without blank nodes, execution remains linear, but recursion increases with blank nodes. Algorithm 1 efficiently manages this process. For example, given `?s = Patient:1`, outgoing connections follow `?s ?p1 ?o1` and incoming `?o1 ?p1 ?s`.

Algorithm 1: Recursive downstream RDF node expansion

```

Input: Source IRI s, depth d
Result: List of elements as (source, edge, target)
1 initialization;
2 Curr ← s; // Current
3 for i ← 0 to d do
4   | Pattern add {?Curr ?Predi ?Obji};
5   | Curr ← Obji;
6 end
7 QRes ← execute query with Pattern; // Result
8 for i ← 0 to QRes.length do
9   | if QResi[Objd-1] is a blank node then
10  | | ResList add all DownstreamExpansion(s, d + 1)
11  | else
12  | | ResList add
13  | | (QResi[Curr], QResi[Predd-1], QResi[Objd-1])
13  | end
14 end
15 return ResultList

```

While the downstream expansion reveals outgoing edges, an analogous algorithm is used for upstream expansion, which displays incoming edges relative to the source. The functionality remains the same, but operates in the opposite direction

⁴<https://github.com/dbai-tuw/fhirdatify-thesis>

⁵<https://angular.dev/>

⁶<https://spring.io/projects/spring-boot>

⁷<https://graphdb.ontotext.com/>

⁸<https://rdf4j.org/>

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF RDF VISUALIZATION TOOLS

Tool	Graph-based	SPARQL Support	Interactive	RDF Instances	Ontology Support	FHIR Specialized
RDF Grapher	Yes	No	No	Yes	Limited	No
WebVOWL	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
YASGUI	No	Yes	Partial	Yes	Yes	No
Wikidata Query Service	Yes	Partial	Yes	Yes	Limited	No
FHIR Lens	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Fig. 1. FHIR Lens main interface

by searching for the reverse pattern in line 4 and expanding in the reverse direction in line 12.

V. EXAMPLE USE CASE

FHIR Lens’ graphical interface enables users to interact efficiently with FHIR data, offering multiple modules for data exploration, SPARQL querying, and statistical visualization.

A typical use case begins with a user selecting a resource from the graph. The selection process is facilitated by an autocomplete feature, which streamlines navigation through the data. Upon choosing a resource, such as `Patient/T0001`, the interface initially presents a graph containing only the selected node and its direct attributes displayed in a structured format. At this stage, the graph remains in a minimal state, allowing the user to focus on the core resource without distractions.

The user can expand the selected node by interacting with the graphical interface to explore relationships and connected entities. Double-clicking on `Patient/T0001` initiates the expansion process, revealing additional nodes that are directly connected to it. As illustrated in Fig. 2, the expanded view includes neighboring nodes, providing insight into various linked entities such as medical records, prescriptions, or associated healthcare providers.

For instance, when the user selects `Patient/1`, an RDF representation of an FHIR patient resource, only core attributes like name, birth date, and gender are initially visible. Expanding the node reveals related resources, such as `Observation/45` (blood pressure measurement) and

Fig. 2. Exploration graph after expansion of `Patient/T0001`

`Encounter/12` (a recent healthcare visit). Further interaction allows access to details like systolic and diastolic values from `Observation/45` or the prescribing physician of `MedicationRequest/78`, enabling structured exploration of interconnected clinical data.

The exploration process does not limit the resources a user can investigate simultaneously. Multiple resources can be selected and visualized in parallel, allowing users to compare different entities within the dataset. The color-coding of nodes enhances the clarity of connections by distinguishing between expanded and unexpanded elements. This design choice ensures that users can maintain context while navigating the RDF graph.

Beyond graphical exploration, the system offers an integrated SPARQL playground, enabling users to execute custom queries on the dataset. This feature is particularly useful for extracting structured information that may not be immediately visible in the graph representation. For example, one can query the graph to count the number of patients with a specific observation type.

Query results can be leveraged to generate statistical visualizations, aiding in data-driven decision-making. The platform supports the creation of charts based on SPARQL query outputs, allowing users to derive analytical insights from RDF data. Charts can have multiple y-axis properties. An example of such a chart, presenting the number of instances per class, is shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Custom query for database statistics

VI. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In this section, we evaluate the load times of the different visualization tools under increased stress.

A. Evaluation Setup

We deployed our system on a Lenovo PC with an Intel Core 16-core Ultra 7 CPU, 64 GB RAM, and an NVMe Disk running Windows 11 Professional. Our test datasets (Table II) comprise a basic sample dataset of 4 patients (1), partial and full sets of real patient graphs (2, 3, 5), and synthetic datasets (4, 6, 7). Performance evaluation was done using

Fig. 4. Average load time performance on three tasks.

the internal timing system of the Microsoft Edge browser inspection tool, capturing the total elapsed time for completing all front-end and back-end activities. Specifically, we evaluated the following three tasks:

- 1) Auto-completion of the search terms *Patient/T*, *Measurement*, and *Condition* in the database exploration screen.
- 2) Loading the database statistics screen with three pre-saved charts: instances-per-class, predicate usage count, and literal type count.
- 3) Expanding a random patient node by two degrees of expansion.

Tasks 2 and 3 were repeated three times for each dataset with the browser cache deactivated.

B. Results

Load times are plotted against the number of patients in the graph in Figure 4. Node expansion times remain relatively stable at around 400ms for the real-world graphs and 1000ms for the synthetic graphs. The time to load full-graph statistics increases polynomially with the number of patients ($R^2 = 0.996$ for a level 2 polynomial fitted curve) but remains a reasonable 12.5 seconds even for the largest 10,000 patient graph. Auto-completion queries for cache-misses demonstrate a sharp linear increase in load time for large graphs, reaching several minutes for the largest patient graphs.

TABLE II
EVALUATION DATASETS

Dataset	Patients	Edges	Density (Edg./Pat.)
1	4	1,043	261
2	889	168,302	189
3	1,782	302,437	170
4	2,500	1,835,557	734
5	3,389	2,003,757	591
6	5,000	3,675,778	735
7	10,000	7,347,734	735

C. Discussion

Node expansion times are directly proportional to the graph's average density. Since synthetic graphs contain in-

formation for all edge types, they are denser than the real-world graph, where different patients are missing data in different ways. However, load times are remarkably robust, allowing exploration to scale easily with graph size. The system seems to be hampered by the performance of auto-completion queries, which leaves much to be desired. This phenomenon is especially salient in queries where the term is not found (e.g., Measurement), requiring the graph database to search all nodes exhaustively. The performance of the statistics page and its custom graphs declines with graph size, which is to be expected; however, it is not unreasonable for an offline large-scale analysis. Analysis of system resources showed that the graph database did not utilize more than 300MB of RAM and 10% of available CPU resources, leading us to conclude that optimization of query resource allocation or full-text indexes could further improve performance.

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presents *FHIR Lens*, an interactive RDF-based visualization platform for FHIR resources, addressing interoperability challenges of healthcare data. It enhances traditional table-based representations by offering a dynamic interface for exploring complex healthcare relationships. Key contributions include recursive algorithms for handling blank nodes, SPARQL-driven querying for semantic retrieval, and an interactive graph-based interface. The platform enables users to dynamically expand, collapse, and explore FHIR resources, making it particularly useful for analyzing patient records, treatments, and observations.

Our future work will further optimize recursive algorithms for scalability, enhance real-time performance and data quality [28], apply the work in the context of personal medicine [29], and incorporate machine learning [30] to enable predictive modeling, trend detection, and advanced healthcare analytics. In terms of performance, we can evaluate methods for speeding up term-completion queries using custom data structures populated for this purpose.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. Lanthaler, D. Wood, and R. Cyganiak, "RDF 1.1 concepts and abstract syntax," W3C, W3C Recommendation, feb 2014, <https://www.w3.org/TR/2014/REC-rdf11-concepts-20140225/>.
- [2] T. Bray, "The JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) Data Interchange Format," RFC 8259, IETF, Tech. Rep. 8259, dec 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://www.rfc-editor.org/info/rfc8259>
- [3] J. Cowan, M. Sperberg-McQueen, T. Bray, F. Yergeau, J. Paoli, and E. Maler, "Extensible markup language (XML) 1.1 (second edition)," W3C, W3C Recommendation, aug 2006, <https://www.w3.org/TR/2006/REC-xml11-20060816/>.
- [4] D. Cotter and V. Bumgardner, "Semantic enrichment of streaming healthcare data," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1912.00423*, 2019.
- [5] E. Prud'hommeaux, J. Collins, D. Booth, K. J. Peterson, H. R. Solbrig, and G. Jiang, "Development of a FHIR RDF data transformation and validation framework and its evaluation," *Journal of biomedical informatics*, vol. 117, p. 103755, 2021.
- [6] A. Walinjar and J. Woods, "FHIR tools for healthcare interoperability," *Biomedical Journal of Scientific and Technical Research*, vol. 9, no. 5, 2018.
- [7] J. Gruendner, C. Gulden, M. Kampf, S. Mate, H.-U. Prokosch, J. Zierk *et al.*, "A framework for criteria-based selection and processing of fast healthcare interoperability resources (FHIR) data for statistical analysis: design and implementation study," *JMIR medical informatics*, vol. 9, no. 4, p. e25645, 2021.
- [8] A. Scherp, G. Gröner, P. Skoda, K. Hose, and M. Vidal, "Semantic Web: Past, Present, and Future," *TGDK*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 3:1–3:37, 2024.
- [9] M. J. Dürst and M. Suignard, "Internationalized Resource Identifiers (IRIs)," RFC 3987, IETF, Tech. Rep. 3987, jan 2005. [Online]. Available: <https://www.rfc-editor.org/info/rfc3987>
- [10] L. Chen, H. Zhang, Y. Chen, and W. Guo, "Blank nodes in rdf," *J. Softw.*, vol. 7, no. 9, pp. 1993–1999, 2012.
- [11] T. Gruber, "Ontology," in *Encyclopedia of Database Systems*, L. Liu and M. T. Özsu, Eds. Springer-Verlag, 2009, <https://tomgruber.org/writing/definition-of-ontology/>.
- [12] D. L. McGuinness and F. van Harmelen, "OWL web ontology language overview," World Wide Web Consortium (W3C), Tech. Rep., February 2004, <http://www.w3.org/TR/2004/REC-owl-features-20040210/>.
- [13] Health Level Seven International, "FHIR Resource Description Framework (RDF) Representation," 2023, accessed: 2025-03-26. [Online]. Available: <https://www.hl7.org/fhir/rdf.html>
- [14] S. Harris and A. Seaborne, "SPARQL 1.1 query language," W3C, W3C Recommendation, mar 2013, <https://www.w3.org/TR/2013/REC-sparql11-query-20130321/>.
- [15] T. M. Fruchterman and E. M. Reingold, "Graph drawing by force-directed placement," *Software: Practice and experience*, vol. 21, no. 11, pp. 1129–1164, 1991.
- [16] T. Kamada, S. Kawai *et al.*, "An algorithm for drawing general undirected graphs," *Information processing letters*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 7–15, 1989.
- [17] E. R. Gansner and S. C. North, "Improved force-directed layouts," in *International Symposium on Graph Drawing*. Springer, 1998, pp. 364–373.
- [18] K. Sugiyama, S. Tagawa, and M. Toda, "Methods for visual understanding of hierarchical system structures," *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 109–125, 1981.
- [19] yWorks, "Hierarchical layout," https://docs.yworks.com/yfiles-html/dguide/layout/hierarchical_layout.html, accessed: 2024-11-10.
- [20] A. Ng, M. Jordan, and Y. Weiss, "On spectral clustering: Analysis and an algorithm," *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 14, 2001.
- [21] H. N. Gabow, "Path-based depth-rst search for strong and biconnected components," *Information Processing Letters*, 2000.
- [22] M. Girvan and M. E. Newman, "Community structure in social and biological networks," *Proceedings of the national academy of sciences*, vol. 99, no. 12, pp. 7821–7826, 2002.
- [23] S. E. Schaeffer, "Graph clustering," *Computer science review*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 27–64, 2007.
- [24] Linked Data Finland, "RDF Grapher," <https://www.ldf.fi/service/rdf-grapher>, accessed: 20-1-2025.
- [25] S. Lohmann, V. Link, E. Marbach, and S. Negru, "WebVOWL: Web-based Visualization of Ontologies," in *EKAW (Satellite Events)*, 2014, pp. 154–158.
- [26] Triply, "YASGUI - Yet Another SPARQL GUI," <https://yasgui.triply.cc/>, accessed: 20-1-2025.
- [27] Wikidata Contributors, "Wikidata Query Service," <https://query.wikidata.org/>, accessed: 2024-11-25.
- [28] K. Rabbani, M. Lissandrini, and K. Hose, "Extraction of Validating Shapes from very large Knowledge Graphs," *Proc. VLDB Endow.*, vol. 16, no. 5, pp. 1023–1032, 2023.
- [29] S. Ortega-Martorell, I. Olier, M. Ohlsson, and G. Y. Lip, "TARGET: A Major European Project Aiming to Advance the Personalised Management of Atrial Fibrillation-Related Stroke via the Development of Health Virtual Twins Technology and Artificial Intelligence," *Thrombosis and Haemostasis*, vol. 125, no. 1, pp. 7–11, 2024.
- [30] E. R. Hansen, T. Sagi, and K. Hose, "Multimodal representation learning for medical analytics - a systematic literature review," *Health Informatics J.*, vol. 30, no. 4, 2024.